

CHARACTERIZATION AND LONG TERM STABILITY ANALYSIS AT PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES WITH SHINGLED CELL STRINGS

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ABSTRACT:

In the last recent years the photovoltaic module design becomes more and more in the research focus to increase the module efficiency. Thereby the optimising of cell interconnection plays a major role since it affects the serial resistance and the power output at higher irradiation levels. A novel interconnection approach is the shingling of solar cell. In this work we characterised and studied the long term stability of commercial shingled pv modules. For its we created a special test sequence for shingled panels. Our results are focused on the low-light performance and compared that to outdoor measurements. As well as the mechanical stability by applying different stress tests. This paper ends in a weak-point-analysis of currently available shingled pv panels with different electrical layouts.

Keywords: reliability, interconnection, shingled

1 INTRODUCTION

Shingled modules have the potential to reach high cell-to-module (CTM) values [1]. This kind of interconnection allows more creativity by engineering the electrical layouts. On cell level the cut processes should be understand and developed to reduce the cut edge recombination [2]. For its two technologies are currently under development. These are called Thermal Laser Separation (TLS) and Lasering and Cutting (L&C). Also a higher hot spot risk was report in the event of shadowing at some electrical layouts [3]. The quality key at shingled designs lies in the properties of the Electrically Conductive Adhesives (ECA). It has to be conductive and mechanical flexible at the same time. Therefore we did investigations on that at different commercial modules.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Test Samples

The investigations we has been done on five commercial available full size pv modules with shingled solar cell strings. The general information about the panels are shown in Table 1. However, detailed information of the BOM's and process parameter are unknown.

Table I: General information of the tested modules.

	Brand "A"	Brand "B"	Brand "C"	Brand "D"	Brand "E"
P_{max} Label	320 W	330 W	340 W	335 W	365 W
Frontend	ARC-Glass	ARC-Glass	ARC-Glass	ARC-Glass	ARC-Glass
Enc.	unknown	unknown	unknown	Unknown	EVA
Cell Type	mono c-Si PERC				
Shingled cell cut	1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5	1/5
Interconnection	serial-parallel	serial-parallel	serial-parallel	serial-parallel	serial-parallel-serial
Backend	black Backsheet	black Backsheet	black Backsheet	white Backsheet	black Backsheet
Module Size	1.0 x 1.7 m ²	1.0 x 1.6 m ²	1.0 x 1.6 m ²	1.0 x 1.7 m ²	1.1 x 1.6 m ²

The electrical layouts of the different brands are displayed in Table 2.

Table II: Electrical layouts of the modules.

2.1 Test Sequences

The following test sequence (Figure 1) was developed and applied to characterize and study the long term stability of the shingled modules.

Figure 1: Applied test sequence.

Four modules per brand were initial characterized (STC & Weak light behaviour, EL). Afterwards one module per brand was outdoor installed for performance comparison and another one mechanical stress tested. Therefore the module centre was blended for 10 cm and then a mechanical load stress test according the IEC were applied. To determine the changes in the quality IV-Curves and EL images were initial and after each test taken.

3 RESULTS

The weak light behavior of the different brands is shown in Figure 2. There the average of four modules per brand is displayed.

Figure 2: Weak light behavior of shingled modules.

The rel. efficiency losses to 1,000 W/m² were determined on the base of low light measurements at 700, 400, 200 and 100 W/m². The standard deviations between the four modules per brand is negligibly small. So that there is a uniform quality. The weak light behavior can be divided into two groups:

- a) Group 1: Brand “C”
- b) Group 2: Other brands

By studying the curve of Brand “C” it can be supposed that it this type has a higher series resistance which results in a better weak light behavior compared to the other brands. At that point it is speculative to say what the reasons are for the higher R_s . Of course it can shingled specific properties like the conductivity of the ECA, the geometry size of the ECA contacting (punctual or linear), cut edge recombination related or it relates to general aspects of the solar cell / module. However, a clear trend that it has do with the length of the strings couldn't find since brand “B” has the same electrical design as brand “C”.

The ranges between that measuring points in Figure 2 were fitted with the following model [4]:

$$rel \eta_{loss} = \frac{V_{oc}(E_e) \cdot I_{sc}(E_e) \cdot FF(E_e) \cdot \frac{1000W}{m^2}}{V_{oc} \cdot I_{sc} \cdot FF \cdot \frac{1000W}{m^2}} - 1 \quad (1)$$

This fitting were necessary to calculate the European η_{Euro} and California Energy Commission η_{CEC} efficiencies. These are defined as:

$$\eta_{Euro} = 0.03 \cdot \eta_{5\%} + 0.06 \cdot \eta_{10\%} + 0.13 \cdot \eta_{20\%} + 0.10 \cdot \eta_{30\%} + 0.48 \cdot \eta_{50\%} + 0.2 \cdot \eta_{100\%} \quad (2)$$

$$\eta_{CEC} = 0.04 \cdot \eta_{10\%} + 0.05 \cdot \eta_{20\%} + 0.12 \cdot \eta_{30\%} + 0.21 \cdot \eta_{50\%} + 0.53 \cdot \eta_{75\%} + 0.05 \cdot \eta_{100\%} \quad (3)$$

The η_{Euro} is an averaged operating efficiency over a yearly power distribution corresponding to middle-Europe climate, while the η_{CEC} is for climates of higher irradiation intensity corresponding to California climate like US south-west regions.

Figure 3: STC, European and California Energy Commission efficiencies.

Based on the different efficiencies definitions, it can be conclude that all brands except brand “C” are more suitable for clear sky regions. To see how comparable these data are to realistic outdoor situations - the modules were outdoor for energy yield measurements installed. The environmental conditions of a clear sky day are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Global irradiance on module level and ambient temperature of a clear sky day (16/08/2020) in Berlin / Germany.

The environmental profiles were taken with an interval of $dt = 5$ sec. Figure 4 shows the quasi perfect sky clear irradiance profile. The average day temperature was $T_{amb} = 30^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 5: Specific energy yield [kWh/kWp] relativized to Brand “E” for a clear sky day in Berlin Germany (16/08/2020). The modules are relativized to Brand “E” because it reached to highest specific energy yield on that day.

The yield results of the clear sky day presented in Figure 5 are comparable to the η_{CEC} efficiency ranking in Figure 3. Brand “E” has the highest yield at sunny days. However, to study the impact of the different weak lights on the energy yield for year, the electrical and thermal module properties were implemented into PVsyst and the performance was simulated for Berlin / Germany (diffuse location) and Seville / Spain (clear sky location). The simulations were done for brand “C” and brand “A”.

Figure 5: Simulated specific energy yield for Berlin / Germany (diffuse location) and Seville / Spain (clear sky location).

Figure 5 shows as expected that the specific energy yields are higher for brand “C” independently of the diffuse rate. Due to the different thermal module properties it isn’t clearly that the yield differences are based on the weak light behaviour or one other effects. Therefore a more detailed study were done (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Thermal and weak light related losses for Berlin / Germany (diffuse location) and Seville / Spain (clear sky location).

Figure 6 displays that at both locations the thermal losses are higher than the weak light related ones. In Spain the thermal losses are even higher than for Germany. Also it becomes clear that brand “C” has lower weak light losses at both locations. Finally, the better weak light of brand “C” gets most visible by comparison the German vs Spain. Between both locations, there is a factor of 3x in the weak light related losses.

As in Figure 1 displayed we applied the bending test before we did the mechanical test according IEC 61215 standard (5x 2400 Pa and 1x 5400 Pa) to one of modules per manufacturer. The bending test isn’t part of the IEC classification but it given an information about the flexibility as well as the conductivity of the

interconnection. During the test condition the module centre is bended 1 cm while its stands in the flasher and the IV-curve and the EL image is taken.

Brand "A"	Initial EL	EL @ Bending
	EL after Bending	EL after ML
Brand "B"	Initial EL	EL @ Bending
	EL after Bending	EL after ML

Brand "C"	Initial EL	EL @ Bending
	EL after Bending	EL after ML
Brand "D"	Initial EL	EL @ Bending
	EL after Bending	EL after ML
Brand "E"	Initial EL	EL @ Bending

Figure 7: EL images (tested at I_{sc}) at different test stages: a) Initial, b) at bending, c) after bending, d) after ML

The detailed analysis of the images could observed the following typical patterns at shingled modules.

Figure 8: EL images of a locally interconnection problem and cell mismatch due to different cell sizes.

At brand “D” we could observed a higher EL signal at the pseudo rectangular cell compared to the full rectangular ones. The higher signal is based on a higher current density at this cells and results in electrical mismatch of cells at normal operations. As well as into a lower CTM-value. We also could detect a typical pattern of a local electrical interconnection problem of shingled modules. An example of that kind pattern is exemplary shown in Figure 8 (right). There the part with bad interconnection has a lower EL signal.

The initial images of Brand “A” shows micro cracks at the corner cells. This could be a sign for a mechanical impact at the transport or handling of the modules.

Figure 7: EL images of a module with mechanical impact (possible a transport or handling related impact).

The further pictures in Figure 8 show the EL images at different test stages. At all modules we noticed only a negligible mechanical impact of the bending test. However, a major impact of the ML-Test could detect on the module designs with long cell strings (Brand “A” and “D”). There the force impact is quite clear due to the position of the broken cells visible. At the modules with the short strings (Brand “B” and “C”) there is quasi no influence visible. Brand “E” has some broken cells in the middle at the short edge. The not changed EL images at the modules with the short cell strings can be described with the force absorption of the ECA and / or the encapsulation material due to its resilience and the short edge length of the cells in direction of the force impact. We want to point out that the limiting stress factor is the ECA and the encapsulation material tensile strength. Due to the brittleness of the silicon and the fact of a quasi-nonexistence buffer zone at the long cell string modules show that a high number of cracked cells.

Figure 9: Power loss at different test stages: a) Initial, b) at bending, c) after bending, d) after ML

P_{max} is changing quite similar to the number of cell cracks in the EL images at the modules with long cell strings (Brand “A” & “D”). The modules with the short strings “C” & “D” have different power losses. While module “B” has a power loss up to -1.9% but no major damages in the EL image visible. Brand “E” has the highest power loss. However, all modules show the power loss <5% after the mechanical impact and therefore they all would pass the IEC criterion.

4 SUMMARY

We have characterized and stressed different commercial shingled modules. Thereby we were focused on the weak light and the mechanical stability. Considering we low light analyse we have to point out: All modules per brand has a similar weak light behaviour (same quality). We could spilt the brands into two groups: Group 1: has a better low-light performance due to a higher R_s . Group 2: has a worse low-light performance due to a lower R_s .

Group 1 is optimized for more diffuse light regions while Group 2 it is for sunny regions. Our outdoor measurements could confirm that. We haven’t seen a clear

impact of the cell string length as well as the shingled module properties on the low light performance.

In contrast to the mechanical tests there we saw a clear relationship between the stress on short and long shingled cell strings. While the bend test has a negligible mechanical impact on the modules, has the ML-Test a major impact on the module designs with long cell strings. There the force impact is quite clear due to the position of the broken cells visible. At the modules with the short strings there is quasi no influence visible. This can be described with the force absorption of the ECA and the encapsulation material due to its resilience and the short edge length of the cells in direction of the force impact. Therefor we want to point out that the limiting stress factor is the ECA and the encapsulation material tensile strength.

SUMMARY

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